

The ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation at enterprises in projects to strengthen economic and food security: the effectiveness of management decisions

Relevance of the research topic. *The study of the effectiveness of managerial decisions on the implementation of the ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation at enterprises in the projects of strengthening economic and food security is conditioned by the lack of a scientifically based understanding of this process in wartime.*

Formulation of the problem. *The scientific potential of resource conservation management is limited by insufficient attention to specific mechanisms for determining its sources and means of management. The issue of integrating the practice of resource conservation management into the business strategy of economic entities in projects to strengthen economic and food security requires scientific understanding. This issue in the context of modern risks determines the relevance of the research topic.*

Setting the purpose and objectives of the study – *to investigate the peculiarities of ensuring the effectiveness of management decisions on the implementation of the ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation at enterprises in the projects of strengthening economic and food security.*

Research method or methodology. *The article uses the following methods: monographic, abstract–logical, analysis and synthesis, systematization.*

Presentation of the main material (research results). *Therefore, the main guidelines for use in Ukraine, taking into account the state of the national economy, are the more effective use of the financial tools for stimulating resource conservation through management measures at the macro–, meso– and micro–levels, the expansion of sources of funding for state resource conservation projects, improvement of planning, in particular, a responsible attitude towards the formulation of state goals resource conservation programs and achieving effectiveness and efficiency of its mechanism.*

Field of application of results. *The results of the study can be used in the practical activities of enterprises to reduce the negative impact of risks on the ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation.*

Conclusions on the article. *According to the theory of resource conservation management, market mechanisms alone are unable to achieve optimal allocation and efficient use of resources. The development and implementation of management solutions aimed at ensuring resource conservation and their effective use is a combined process based on the use of excellent management methods and tools, corresponding to the current conditions and tasks of the development of enterprises in the projects of strengthening economic and food security.*

Keywords: *ecological and economic mechanism, resource conservation, enterprises, project, economic security, food security, efficiency, management decisions.*

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Еколого–економічний механізм ресурсозбереження на підприємствах в проектах посилення економічної та продовольчої безпеки: ефективність управлінських рішень

Актуальність теми дослідження. *Дослідження ефективності управлінських рішень з реалізації еколого–економічного механізму ресурсозбереження на підприємствах в проектах посилення*

економічної та продовольчої безпеки обумовлюється відсутністю науково обгрунтованого розуміння даного процесу у військовий час.

Постановка проблеми. Науковий потенціал із питань менеджменту ресурсозбереження обмежений недостатньою увагою до конкретних механізмів визначення його джерел та засобів управління. Наукового осмислення потребують питання інтеграції практики менеджменту ресурсозбереження в підприємницьку стратегію економічних суб'єктів в проектах посилення економічної та продовольчої безпеки. Дане питання в контексті сучасних ризиків обумовлює актуальність теми дослідження.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – дослідити особливості забезпечення ефективності управлінських рішень з реалізації еколого–економічного механізму ресурсозбереження на підприємствах в проектах посилення економічної та продовольчої безпеки.

Метод або методологія дослідження. В статті використано наступні методи: монографічний, абстрактно–логічний, аналізу і синтезу, систематизації.

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). Отже, основними орієнтирами використання в Україні з огляду на стан національної економіки є більш дієве задіяння фінансового інструментарію стимулювання ресурсозбереження заходами менеджменту на макро-, мезо- та мікрорівнях, розширення джерел фінансування державних проєктів ресурсозбереження, вдосконалення планування, зокрема, відповідальне ставлення з формулювання цілей державних програм ресурсозбереження та досягнення результативності й ефективності його механізму.

Галузь застосування результатів. Результати дослідження можуть бути використані в практичній діяльності підприємств для зменшення негативного впливу ризиків на еколого–економічний механізм ресурсозбереження.

Висновки за статтею. Згідно теорії менеджменту ресурсозбереження, одні ринкові механізми не в змозі здійснити оптимальний розподіл й ефективне використання ресурсів. Розробка й реалізація управлінських рішень, спрямованих на забезпечення ресурсозбереження та їх ефективне використання, є комбінованим процесом, в основі якого лежить використання відмінних методів та інструментарію менеджменту, відповідного чинним умовам і завданням розвитку підприємств в проектах посилення економічної та продовольчої безпеки.

Ключові слова: еколого–економічний механізм, ресурсозбереження, підприємства, проєкт, економічна безпека, продовольча безпека, ефективність, управлінські рішення.

Formulation of the problem. The scientific potential of resource conservation management is limited by insufficient attention to specific mechanisms for determining its sources and means of management. The issue of integrating the practice of resource conservation management into the business strategy of economic entities in projects to strengthen economic and food security requires scientific understanding. Insufficient attention is paid to the issue of ensuring the investment attractiveness of projects with integrated management measures for resource conservation, which narrows investment activity and hinders the development of natural frugality of resource users. Therefore, a systematic approach to the study of the effectiveness of management decisions of the ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation management is currently needed in order to ensure sustainable development.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Resource conservation is traditionally interpreted as a strategic vector of the functioning of the economy, increasing its competitiveness, efficiency and profitability of economic activity in general both at the level of the country, its regions, industry, and at the level of an individual enterprise. Today, the country faces a number of problems in the field of resource use, in particular: the limitation of most raw resources; aggravation of competition for resources at the domestic and foreign levels; increasing the risks of environmental and man-made disasters; low efficiency of resource management; the emergence of international conflicts caused by the global redistribution of influences and rights, etc. [1–11]. Therefore, the whole complex of problems in the field of resource conservation management becomes an urgent research problem for domestic science, both in terms of improv-

ing the theoretical and methodological foundations of this process, and in terms of practical proposals for the implementation of the mechanism of effective use of the country's resource potential, which is especially relevant in projects to strengthen the economic and food security.

The formulation of the goals of the article is to investigate the peculiarities of ensuring the effectiveness of management decisions on the implementation of the ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation at enterprises in the projects of strengthening economic and food security.

Presenting main material. Analyzing the above approaches to understanding the essence of the ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation, we come to the conclusion that the basic principles of this process are:

- the principles of minimization and maximization, which provide for the achievement of positive activity results under the conditions of reducing the amount of resource use;
- the principle of cyclicity, which reflects the need to organize a reproducible process of resource substitution at each stage of the cycle of creating and promoting an innovative product by reducing costs and replacing one resource with a combination of others [7];
- the principle of singularity, which provides for the priority of organizational and intellectual processes of resource substitution, which will contribute to the improvement of resource conservation management mechanisms;
- factors contributing to the realization of the goal of resource conservation, in particular, technical, organizational–management and socio–economic factors.

Therefore, the meaningful filling of the ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation management includes: rational use of mineral raw materials and fuel resources; introduction of resource–saving equipment and technologies; wide use of man–made waste, especially in the branches of the processing industry of secondary raw materials; restoration and stabilization of the land fund: reviving the fertility of the land, reclamation of obsolete industrial facilities, etc.; effective regulation of forest use, maintenance of forest productivity, active reforestation; preservation of recreational resources when new industrial facilities are placed [11].

At the same time, it is natural factors that are the natural basis, the basis of production, and all others are generated by social production itself. The best results are achieved when a close to optimal or optimal ratio of the listed factors is ensured [6].

Since a person in this interaction acts not simply as a biological being, but always as a member of society, the process of metabolism takes the form of interaction between nature and society. It is obvious that the formation and development of society is connected not simply with the appearance of another branch of the biological cycle, but with the formation of a specific public link in the general cycle of substances on Earth. Only part of the consumed natural material is retained in the form of tools or reusable working capital. Return products inherent in various stages of various production processes are essentially substances that pollute the natural environment.

A resource cycle is a set of transformations and spatial movements of a certain substance that occur at all stages of its use by man and flow within the framework of the public link of the general circulation of this substance on Earth. Resource cycles are distinguished by the types of the main substance involved in them, or a combination of substances. Moreover, each cycle is usually overgrown with a number of accompanying and side sub–cycles, which develop on the basis of versatile use of the main resource and primary natural materials, which are additionally involved in economic turnover [1; 10].

The functioning of this and other cycles based on renewable natural resources is carried out with a rather low coefficient of useful use of primary substances and energy. All over the world, only 2–3% of phyto–biomass produced annually by photosynthesis on land is used by humans [1]. In general, the improvement of each resource cycle at all its stages is the basis of resource conservation management, that is, the use of natural resources without their depletion. Therefore, the main task of forming an effective ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation management is to bring the economic resource cycle closer to the natural one.

Natural ecosystems, in contrast to artificial ones, are characterized, as is known, by a closed cycle of matter. Moreover, the waste associated with the existence of a separate population is the initial material that ensures the existence of another or more than several other populations included in

this biogeocenosis [1]. Nature has historically developed, as a rule, a closed, self-sustaining biological production capable of existing, expanding and improving over an unfathomable time scale, provided that certain environmental parameters are preserved and solar energy is regularly supplied.

The vast majority of existing man-made manufacturing technologies are open systems in which natural resources are irrationally used and large volumes of waste are generated. It is legitimate, based on the deep biophysical analogy between biological and industrial production from the point of view of the mechanism of circulation of substances and energy, to talk about the formation of waste-free and low-waste technologies in anthropogenic production systems.

The cyclical rotation of substances in separate ecosystems and in the entire biosphere, which was formed during its long evolution, is a prototype of ecologically justified production technology.

When we talk about zero-waste technologies, we mean the maximum possible use of raw materials and fuel and energy resources in production without the generation of environmentally harmful waste, reprocessing and disposal of industry waste or neutralizing it before returning to the natural environment.

Low-waste means a method of producing products in which the harmful effect on the environment does not exceed the level permitted by sanitary and hygienic standards [1]. At the same time, for technical, economic, organizational or other reasons, part of the raw materials and materials, determined by industry standards, becomes unused waste and is directed to long-term storage or burial.

The basis of the criteria limiting the harmful effects of low-waste production on the environment are the existing sanitary and hygienic standards – maximum permissible concentrations. Based on them, the scientific and technical norms of the impact of low-waste production on the environment are calculated based on the existing methods, taking into account the totality of factors and possible consequences.

Modern multifunctional production has at its disposal a significant potential base for the implementation of zero-waste and low-waste technological processes that ensure the comprehensive use of secondary raw (material) resources (according to VSR or VMR) and industrial waste from the processing of raw materials [1]. In this way, objective prerequisites are created for a constructive,

purposeful and consistent solution to such serious tasks as increasing production, saving natural resources, protecting the natural environment, which concerns, for example, the development of biogas production.

The main reason why biogas plants have not received proper development in Ukraine is the availability of cheap gas and electricity for a long time. Another reason can be called the relatively low awareness of enterprises in the issue of mineral fertilizer abuse, and the relatively low cost of the latter. Mentality and lack of implementation experience also played a role. Today, these projects are being implemented and their payback period is from 3 to 8 years (depending on the cost of gas and fertilizers).

As a rule, biogas plants are built on the basis of livestock complexes, poultry farms and enterprises for processing agricultural products. They are designed for the processing of various agricultural and food industry wastes and implement the following:

- 1) disposal of waste and improvement of the ecological condition in the areas of production of agricultural products and their processing;
- 2) obtaining energy resources (biogas, electricity, thermal energy);
- 3) production of environmentally friendly organic fertilizers.

Thus, the industry (enterprise) can become energy-independent, provide itself with highly effective fertilizers, and significantly increase profitability due to savings/elimination of a number of cost items. On the one hand, the high efficiency of resource conservation management is achieved due to the withdrawal of land areas from auxiliary industries, on the other hand, conditions are created to reduce dependence on the involved energy resources. On the basis of the above material, the following tasks of the resource-saving policy in agriculture are formulated:

1. Ensuring rational use of material resources.
2. Efforts to create zero-waste production with an intermediate stage of creating low-waste production.
3. Transition to new high-quality technologies that are safer than existing measures of production systems.
4. Provision of innovative programs and technologies, such as resource-saving hitech technology for obtaining scarce energy resources from waste and by-products.

5. Optimization of the structure of resource consumption based on the implementation of new project, design and technological solutions.

The received information about the target priorities for the implementation of resource conservation tasks needs conceptual design in order to determine the driving management principles for the implementation of effective measures in practice.

Since the problem of resource conservation is complex, the implementation of the ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation management involves overcoming a number of existing management and organizational and economic problems: the imperfection of the legislative framework and the work system of state resource conservation management bodies; inadequacy of legal responsibility for overspending of resources; shortage of resource management specialists; lack of developed infrastructure for resource conservation; insufficient material stimulation of resource conservation; insufficient effective use of price tools, which is caused by an increase in the material and resource component of the production cost; unfavorable investment climate; shortage of funds for the development of effective resource-saving technologies; ineffectiveness of protection against unfair competition on the part of foreign producers [5].

Usually, the concepts and theoretical models of resource conservation management are based on the factors of increasing the resource efficiency of production and the resulting resource-saving effects, such as: productivity and innovativeness of production, environmental protection, etc. The existing concepts provide an answer to the question: at the expense of what factors and levers of influence will resource conservation management take place.

Among the modern concepts of the ecological and economic management mechanism of resource conservation, the concept of sustainable development has become the theoretical basis for the development of mankind for the next decades. Green economy was defined as its practical implementation mechanism at the Rio+20 Conference [8].

This concept involves a simple reproduction of the population, the transfer of industrial production and communal services to work with solid waste disposal. The impossibility of implementing this concept necessitated the formation of other concepts that most realistically reflected the in-

terests of various segments of the population and regions. The process of improving the concept was accompanied by the replacement of zero growth with limited growth, and then the emergence of the concept of quality of life, which requires compliance with quality standards of safety and content of work, quality of food products, living conditions, state of health, etc. [3].

The essence of the «factor four» concept involves a four-fold increase in the efficiency of resource use, which implies a 2-fold reduction in resource consumption and a double increase in profit, or a 4-fold increase in profit with the same amount of resources, or an identical profit is obtained with 25% use of resources while reducing environmental pollution environment. The use of resource-saving technologies, advanced engineering and the latest production methods makes it possible to use fewer resources to produce more products. That is, a 4 times greater economic effect is obtained with the number of resources that exist at the moment [9]. The disadvantage of the «factor four» concept can be considered different results obtained from investing in resource-saving technologies. That is, companies are looking for different benefits from this concept.

Factor 10 is a concept of the Wuppertal German Institute. The content of the «factor 10» concept is to shift the focus from the problem of pollutant monitoring to the problem of resource use. Environmental damage is actually caused not only by pollution, but also by resource extraction. In accordance with the «factor 10» concept, investments to increase the level of resource conservation management and create environmentally efficient products are cheaper than unwanted waste, and can also expand production [1].

At the same time, the concept of zero waste (Zero Waste) as an approach to the problem of waste contains 3 distinctive characteristics:

- the starting point here is not the waste sector as such, but the systems of production and consumption, of which waste is a part. At the same time, the object of attention is industrial systems, not the final link of the economic chain;

- the approach to the problem is carried out from the side of the new industrial model – from systemic positions and ideas about the economy as a whole and complex complex multi-purpose production and organizational systems;

– a new model of eco-policy and the process of changes in industry is proposed.

Strategically, the main place in Zero Waste is reserved for the intensive use of secondary raw materials and composting. However, the impact of Zero Waste is more profound: Zero Waste shifts the focus from waste itself to broader projects of industrial transformation. The concept of zero waste includes: zero discharge, zero emission, reduction of waste to zero.

The second principle of Zero Waste is the reduction to zero of damage to the atmosphere, which will largely be solved by banning the sending of untreated waste to the landfill.

Thirdly, Zero Waste is aimed at solving the problem of eliminating waste as such. It can be described most clearly as follows: there will be no more waste that needs to be disposed of in some way. No materials will be considered useless – instead, the way they are used will be accelerated [3].

The main drawback of the concept of zero waste is the focus mainly on the environmental parameters of investing in resource-saving technologies, while the company is primarily interested in the profit from these technologies.

Taking into account the above-mentioned principles of ensuring the effectiveness of management measures for the implementation of the ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation, as well as taking into account the priority desire of business entities to receive profits from resource-saving technologies, the line of concepts should be expanded with a concept of organic farming specific, for example, to the agriculture of Ukraine, which will influence on economic and food security.

Therefore, the above shows that the management of resource conservation should take place taking into account the following principles, which reflect the specifics of resource conservation and underlie the operation of the mechanism for managing this process:

– general principles of nature management, which provides for the maximization of the social utility of natural resources and the greening of production;

– the principle of replacing material and energy resources with intellectual and organizational ones;

– the principle of interconnectedness and synchronization of processes (presupposes the organization of the process of replacing one resource with a combination of others, the use of which in

aggregate creates the effect of reducing costs per unit of consumer properties);

– principle of proportionality of processes of evolutionary and revolutionary approaches in innovative provision of resource conservation management;

– the principle of the need to ensure long-term and systematic development and increase of resources, their transformation into knowledge and their effective management.

Taking into account the above, it is possible to give the following interpretation of the essence of resource conservation management as the organization of effective resource use practices, focused on the effective stimulation of resource saving and waste-free production, which, unlike the existing ones, is implemented through the participation of participants in the agro-food sector on the principles of complementarity and allows for the organization of synergistic interaction of its branches.

In general, taking into account the research of domestic and foreign scientists on the management of resource conservation, it is necessary to look more broadly at the problem and direct managerial influence not purely on the processes of resource conservation, but on the involvement of effective methods of resource management, which should involve the implementation of a number of functions, in particular, planning, organization and regulation of resource use, as well as analysis and control of the results of this activity and its stimulation. Moreover, these functions will be performed at the macro, meso, and microeconomic levels, including through the implementation of sectoral, state, regional, and local development programs.

Foreign countries have extensive experience in ensuring effective resource consumption and implementation of resource conservation management mechanisms. In order to determine ways to improve the efficiency of resource use management in Ukraine, it is important to study this experience because too high a level of resource consumption, an ineffective mechanism of resource use, and environmental pollution make it necessary to find ways to reduce resource costs and their reproduction.

The practice of developed countries shows that the program-target method of resource conservation management is the most effective. It is quite widely used in the USA, Canada, Great Britain, Germany, France, South Korea and other countries, where targeted state and, in particular, budget

programs for resource conservation management are implemented annually. At the same time, the following principles of resource conservation management are followed in highly developed countries:

- improvement of the structure of used resources by reducing the share of export of raw materials, increasing the share of ecologically clean and efficient types of resources;
- increase in mineral extraction rates;
- increasing the share of resource-saving technologies;
- analysis of the use of resources at each stage of the life cycle of objects;
- development of methods of analysis, optimization, forecasting and motivation to improve the use of resources;
- application of effective management in solving resource conservation problems.

The world experience of developing and implementing projects related to effective resource use has in its arsenal a significant variety of mechanisms and economic means of ensuring the efficiency of resource consumption in all spheres of activity, in particular in agriculture [9].

So, the main ways of solving the problems of the mechanism of rational resource consumption can be defined: the development of methods of analysis, forecasting, optimization and stimulation of improving the use of resources; development of regional schemes for efficient use of resources depending on the natural, economic and social features of the territory; creation of regional independent audit and monitoring centers, prevention of environmental pollution based on the use of modern technologies.

The rural economy has a significant potential to involve private initiative in the management of resource conservation by stimulating the development of ecologically oriented farming technologies. However, the main problem remains the development of an effective ecological and economic mechanism of resource conservation management, motivating the process of investing in resource-saving technologies and introducing energy-efficient and energy-saving programs, creating their reliable financial support.

Therefore, as the experience of other countries shows, state support plays a significant role in the formation of innovation and investment policy and opportunities to expand the range of organic market operators. Crop insurance against losses,

preferential lending, subsidizing a part of production costs, a system of subsidies in the transition period and regulation of regional markets of organic products are the main economic measures for the development of small entrepreneurship and the introduction of innovations for subjects of large entrepreneurship in Ukraine.

In addition to producers of organic products, seed and breeding farms, research institutions, ecological consulting services, marketing organizations, ecological inspection and permanent programs for the development of organic agriculture need state support.

Therefore, it is objectively necessary and urgent to solve the problem of resource conservation management in the national economy as well. It should be solved comprehensively at all levels of management [7].

The level of state aid is very important and requires constant attention. When allocating state aid, governments should assume that subsidies should not distort competition in the given sector; on the contrary, state aid should stimulate restructuring and innovation, that is, support investments that lead to increased environmental efficiency of organizations and industries.

The main goal pursued by the current state aid programs is to create incentives for local governments and enterprises to activate environmental protection investments at the expense of their own funds. Because of this, the level of public assistance should be such that it does not replace, but complements the funding provided by the recipient of the assistance itself, and the agencies that carry out public environmental spending programs should be considered as a last resort to help close funding gaps for priority environmental issues. Therefore, subsidies should be minimal [3]. This minimum level can be determined in such a way that it allows to make nature protection projects economically feasible.

The public spending program in the European Union is a mechanism for distributing subsidies in priority areas. In fact, these programs are implemented through specific projects. Given this, the process of developing programs includes the formation of such rules, according to which the program will be executed. First of all, this concerns the procedures related to the evaluation, selection and financing of such projects, with the help of which the stated goals of the program can be achieved.

The programs adopted for the purpose of implementing the environmental policy determine the priority tools, measures on the basis of which these tasks will be solved, as well as the resources corresponding to these tasks, required for the application of these tools.

These tasks can be solved with or without subsidies. From this point of view, the implementation program is divided into 2 parts – one that requires and one that does not require government spending. It should be noted that where subsidies are not needed, the goal is to use conventional environmental protection tools – regulations, taxes, fees, permits, and other regulatory mechanisms [2].

In a broad sense, the software development process includes 2 categories of solutions:

- decisions on the basis of which elements of spending programs are determined, including rules and procedures;
- decisions related to the formation of agency revenues and cash flows.

Thus, environmental protection investment programs represent the implementation component of the corresponding financial management strategy developed to support the goals of sustainable development.

As a result of the generalization and analysis of foreign experience in the financial support of resource conservation management projects, it was established that the developed countries of the world have and are consistently implementing resource conservation management programs at the national, regional, and industry levels. This experience shows that the program–target method of budget management for resource conservation is the most effective. Special attention is paid to the evaluation of the effectiveness and efficiency of these programs. To carry out this assessment, budget programs are systematically monitored, taking into account general scientific approaches and the specifics of the conditions of a certain country.

The implementation of foreign experience in financing resource–saving measures should solve the problem of ineffective financial support for the implementation of resource–saving management projects in Ukraine. For this, it is possible to apply, for example, the experience of the United States, which consists in establishing such tax benefits aimed at ensuring high efficiency of energy consumption in all areas; the experience of the countries of Central

and Eastern Europe [1], when the government supported exactly those investment projects that are economically and/or ecologically appropriate and cannot be financed from other sources. Constant monitoring of the effectiveness of financial support during all stages of program implementation can also be considered a defining feature of the practice of implementing resource–saving management programs abroad. Constant monitoring of the effectiveness of financial support makes it possible to adjust the financial and economic mechanism and sources of financial support.

The international practice of the World Bank on the implementation of energy efficiency programs is fully applied in countries with a low and/or middle income level [3; 7]. Ukraine can also receive analytical and advisory services to ensure environmentally sustainable energy development through a combination of different types of financial support.

Also adapted for implementation may be preferential financing programs (China), loans on loyal terms (Germany, India), the activities of Energy Efficiency Improvement Funds, which provide financing for energy efficiency improvement projects to public customers with the return of funds from saved energy (Armenia, Bulgaria), public loans on preferential terms in commercial institutions for re–crediting by municipalities for energy efficiency improvement projects (Poland, Serbia, Turkey), supplier loans, commercial loans made through energy service companies (Canada, the Czech Republic, Japan).

Therefore, the main guidelines for use in Ukraine, taking into account the state of the national economy, are the more effective use of the financial tools for stimulating resource conservation through management measures at the macro–, meso– and micro–levels, the expansion of sources of funding for state resource conservation projects, improvement of planning, in particular, a responsible attitude towards the formulation of state goals resource conservation programs and achieving effectiveness and efficiency of its mechanism.

Conclusions. According to the theory of resource conservation management, market mechanisms alone are unable to achieve optimal allocation and efficient use of resources. The development and implementation of management solutions aimed at ensuring resource conservation and their effective use is a combined process based on the use of excellent management methods and tools, cor–

responding to the current conditions and tasks of the development of enterprises in the projects of strengthening economic and food security.

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МАРЧЕНКО В. М.
КОЛЕСНИК М. В.
ОСТАПЕНКО Т. Г.

Світовий досвід реалізації державних організаційно–економічних підходів до розвитку сучасних процесів кластеризації

Мета статті полягає в узагальненні участі держави у створенні та підтримці кластерів та типології підходів держави в реалізації кластерного розвитку. Об'єктами дослідження обрано дві групи країн: 1) країни з тривалою історією розвитку кластерів (США, Італія, Китай); 2) країни Центральної Азії, які перебувають на стадії початку формування кластерів (Узбекистан, Киргизстан). Результати дослідження дозволяють систематизувати інструменти державного впливу на забезпечення умов для формування нових та підтримання продуктивності існуючих кластерів на зруйнованих територіях України в період післявоєнної відбудови економіки країни.

Методологія проведення роботи. В дослідженні використані методи узагальнення та систематизації.